

Awareness, Knowledge and Utilization of Educational Mobile Applications in Teaching among Public Secondary School Teachers in Anambra State

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ABSTRACT

Mobile Applications utilization in teaching is becoming an important tool for improving efficiency and eliminating barriers of time and distance in modern time teaching globally. Against this backdrop, this study examined the knowledge and utilization of educational mobile applications in teaching among public secondary school teachers in Anambra State. The study was situated within the framework of Diffusion of Innovation and Technological Determinism theory. The quantitative design (survey) adopted. Applying the Krejcie and Morgan (1979) parameter for sample size determination, a sample of 399 was drawn from a population of 5523 public secondary school teachers in Anambra State. The three selected public secondary schools were Capital City Secondary School Awka, Eastern Academy Onitsha and Awada Secondary School Obosi using simple random sampling procedure. A structured questionnaire was designed for the survey data collection. Findings revealed that although an average percentage of public secondary school teachers are aware of the educational mobile applications in teaching, many do not utilize it in teaching due to a poor knowledge of the educational mobile applications and due to the fact that it is yet to be integrated in their teaching method. Some teachers also utilize social media application to communicate and teach students by sending lesson notes to students. Other challenges of poor utilization include poor internet access, unavailability of requisite devices such as mobile phones, low knowledge of the benefits of educational mobile applications and poor funding, poor sensitizations, workshops or training on the benefits of utilizing educational mobile applications in teaching among public secondary school teachers in Anambra State. The study recommended, amongst others that there should be enlightenment programmes including workshop and seminars to orientate the public secondary school teachers on the benefits of utilizing the educational mobile applications in teaching.

Keywords: *Awareness, Knowledge, Utilization, Educational Mobile Applications, Teaching, Teachers*

1.1 Introduction

Education as one of the basic functions of mass communication has witnessed a rapid change in the 21st century especially with regards to classroom teaching which involves the integration of mobile application. Obineme, Eziamaka and Mbonu (2024) noted that ICT integration has a significant impact on students' academic performances. In this vein, Nwajioha (2025) stated that teachers' attitudes toward ICT integration in teaching are crucial for effective teaching and management. The twenty-first century has brought a technological revolution which is continuously evolving towards powerful mobile and hand-held devices as well as intelligent software applications which are improving on our quality of lives.

Consequently, one could attest to the fact that the new wave of computer technologies has impacted positively in our education system by ushering in alternative ways of teaching like using computers, mobile applications and its related gadgets, internet connectivity, video, simulations, television, social media technologies that suit the needs of the subject. It is seen as one of the indispensable tools or a powerful force in achieving an effective classroom delivery in our educational system. This came with enormous changes that have influenced teaching and knowledge given by teachers.

Incorporation of educational mobile applications in secondary education is a laudable move as it has continued to play significant role in teachers' lesson delivery. Its importance in secondary school education cannot be overemphasized. Teachers in modern times have developed new abilities, perceptions and approaches to teaching. Therefore, it becomes imperative that the system of education adapts to the new method of Information Communication and Technology usage, and knowledge transfer approaches (Okafor & Obikwelu, 2019) which includes the use of educational mobile applications.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

The integration of technology into education has become increasingly essential, particularly with the global push for digital learning and blended instructional models. In Nigeria, and specifically in Anambra State, the adoption of educational mobile applications among public secondary school teachers remains relatively underexplored and underutilized (Okeke & Nwafor, 2023). While mobile apps such as Google Classroom offer promising avenues for enhancing student engagement and learning outcomes, anecdotal evidence and limited empirical studies suggest that their use in classroom instruction is inconsistent and sometimes resisted (Ezeokoli & Ugwuanyi, 2022).

Despite national education policies emphasizing digital literacy and ICT integration, many teachers in public secondary schools' face challenges related to digital competence, access to resources, and institutional support (Nwachukwu & Ofojebe, 2024). These issues hinder the effective use of educational mobile technologies in teaching, despite increasing use of smartphones and mobile apps outside the classroom for informal learning. Moreover, a noticeable gap exists between the potential of mobile applications to transform teaching and their current level of implementation in Nigerian classrooms, which raises concerns about the quality of education delivery and its alignment with global education trends (Uzochukwu, 2023).

Consequently, there is a critical need to investigate how, and to what extent, public secondary school teachers in Anambra State are aware, knowledgeable and utilize educational mobile

applications in teaching. Such a study is vital to uncover the underlying factors that influence educational mobile application adoption, assess the challenges teachers face, and identify best practices that can inform policy and training programs aimed at improving technology integration in teaching. Without this empirical understanding, efforts to enhance digital teaching practices may remain ineffective or unsustainable.

Against this backdrop, this study examined the awareness, knowledge and utilization of educational mobile applications in teaching among public secondary school teachers in Anambra State.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

The purpose of this study was to ascertain the level of educational mobile applications awareness, knowledge and utilization in teaching among public secondary school teachers in Anambra State. Specifically, the study targeted the following objectives:

1. To ascertain the level of awareness of teachers in public secondary schools in Anambra State on the benefits of utilizing educational mobile applications in teaching.
2. To determine the extent teachers in public secondary schools in Anambra State are knowledgeable about educational mobile applications in teaching.
3. To find out specific areas of utilization of educational mobile applications by teachers in public secondary schools in teaching in Anambra State.
4. To discover possible problems arising from their use of educational mobile applications in teaching.

1.4 Research Questions

Based on the above objectives, the following research questions were formulated to guide the study.

1. To what extent are teachers in public secondary schools in Anambra State aware of the benefits of utilizing educational mobile applications in teaching?
2. To what extent are teachers in public secondary schools in Anambra State knowledgeable about utilization of educational mobile applications in teaching?
3. What are the specific areas of utilization of educational mobile applications in teaching among public secondary schools in Anambra State?
4. What are the possible constraints to utilization of educational mobile applications in teaching among public secondary schools' teachers in Anambra State?

1.5 Scope of Study.

This study centered on awareness, knowledge and utilization of educational mobile applications in teaching among public secondary school teachers in Anambra State. The secondary schools in question are those owned by the government of Anambra State, which is regarded in this work as public secondary schools. The work was carried out in Anambra state with a population of over five thousand, five hundred and twenty three teachers (PPSCC, 2024).

Generally, this study is limited to awareness, knowledge and utilization of educational mobile applications in teaching among public secondary school teachers in Anambra State. Despite the need for generalization, the study is delimited to the sample size for the generalization of the study.

1.6 Significance of Study

In spite of, the existence of several studies on the issue of educational mobile applications usage, there is still need to look at educational mobile applications utilization pattern among public

secondary school teachers in teaching which includes the aspect of impacting knowledge to students for easier understanding, receiving lessons retrieval purposes and also breaching the challenge of distance between the teacher and the learner as the case may be.

However, it is expected that the output of this research work benefits those working in public secondary schools, the ministry of education and all those who teach younger people especially at the primary and secondary level as the research shows the relevance of proper utilization of educational mobile applications in teaching. Also, this work provides more knowledge on the benefits and as well as the challenges of utilizing educational mobile applications in teaching, providing guidance for addressing these issues and maximizing the potential of these apps.

This study shall be of great significance to the various key stakeholders in secondary education in Anambra State. They include; the Anambra State government policy makers, Post Primary Schools Service Commission (PPSSC), Principals, Teachers, Students, Parents Teachers Association (PTA), Alumni, Curriculum developers and other researchers. To the Anambra State government and policy makers in the education sector, the findings of this present study acquaints them towards understanding the extent to which these educational mobile applications are necessary for teacher development, job performance and school improvement.

Furthermore, the study shall facilitate a transition to mobile teaching among public secondary school teachers, encourages mobile teaching with ease and help teachers understand how best to sustain the learner's attention, manage barriers of locations through using the educational mobile applications. Upon successful completion of this work, it hopes to contribute to the existing literature in new media and be relevant to various academics within and across Nigeria.

2.1 Education in the Era of Online Technologies

Education, a specialized training given to individuals with the basic aim of equipping them with the knowledge of reading, writing and calculation, as well as specialized skills for developing their interest and ability has gone to the level of adopting the use of technologies to achieve this, which still requires the skills needed to utilize the mobile application and other technological devices that are used. The acquisition of these skills and competencies enable individuals to achieve self-development and contribute effectively towards social development (Okeke, 2016, pp.24-25).

The world of education is currently undergoing a massive transformation as a result of the digital revolution. This transformation is similar to the transition from apprenticeship to universal schooling that occurred in the 19th century as a result of the industrial revolution. In the apprenticeship era, most of what people learned occurred outside of school. Universal schooling led people to identify learning with school, but now the identification of the two is unraveling. All around us, people are been taught with the aid of new technologies: children are playing complex video games, workers are interacting with simulations that put them in challenging situations, students are taking courses at online high schools and colleges, and adults are consulting Wikipedia. New technologies create learning opportunities that challenge traditional schools and colleges. These new learning niches enable people of all ages to pursue education in their own terms.

2.2 Educational Mobile Application: An Overview

The term "Educational Mobile Application" is one that is programmed to function on mobile devices, which may include smartphones, computers and tablets, etc. They serve different needs

for people, as they have been developed to assist humans in performing certain roles and tasks. Mobile application in education are used to support students' learning and teaching, as well as help in providing access to educational resources and facilitate communication and collaboration.

In addition, some studies compared educational mobile applications software related to design, development, affordances and user interface, such as screen colour, size, fonts, customization and adaptability. It was asserted that educational mobile app software should be examined on how effectively and authentically learning experiences are embedded.

Educational mobile application software is an integral part of technology integration. Educational mobile application software directly and closely interacts with learners. It has significantly impacted educational ecosystems through the transformation of formal and non-formal learning (Notari, Hielscher & King, 2016). The affordances and versatilities of educational mobile application software provide prominent opportunities to shift the pedagogy from teacher-centered to student-centered to achieve better learning performance.

2.3 Awareness on Role of Educational Mobile Applications in Teaching

Educational mobile application awareness by teachers is a key factor that leads to their adoption and effective integration and utilization into teaching. This can also be achieved through exposing the teachers to training and providing the necessary tools to improve the awareness and adoption level of the teachers. Interacting with people of like minds and as well enhancing learning without any geographical constraints.

Educational mobile applications have gained attention in recent years due to the ability of improving learning and teaching. Some scholars also are of the opinion that awareness is influenced by their technological pedagogical content knowledge. Educational mobile applications can play a significant role in teaching and learning by increasing the level of students' interest and engagement by providing interactive and immersive teaching experiences will help to facilitate collaborative learning by enabling students to share resources, work on projects and communicate with peers, by also increasing the access to educational resources. Educational mobile applications can increase access by enabling students to have access to digital books and online video courses. (Kumar et al, 2019).

2.4 Benefits of Mobile Applications in teaching

Mobile applications are no longer used for entertainment alone but can also serve educational purposes. It became more popular of its importance as a result of the pandemic that lured schools to adapt to the change of the time. This trend however led to the development of mobile educational applications to support students' learning and teaching by the teachers. These apps provide greater flexibility, accessibility, personalization and real-time feedback, innovation and empowerment, but they also pose some challenges and risks. In a review of research studies of mobile learning in higher education in Africa.

Specifically, it was noted that the use of mobile learning applications enhanced student and lecturer collaboration, students' access to course materials, greater students' control over their learning, student participation and engagement. According to a study by Norries, Hossain & Soloway (2011) Student's performance improves when they use mobile learning devices in class.

Kumar (2011) also added that students make use of the mobile app for reading e-books and downloading online lectures to improve their learning. Woodcock and Middleton (2012) in his study, stated that the use of mobile application improves productivity and eventually their learning performances if they are used for learning purposes.

Some of these impacts include:

- 1. Mobile Applications have redefined teaching:** by making it more personalized, accessible and flexible. They allow teaching at their own pace, receive instant feedback and access various courses and skills from different platforms that offer education on general subject matter, to language and even coding. With features like AI-driven learning paths and gratification, these applications have added to the education sector, offering more opportunities for learners of all ages and backgrounds.
- 2. Personalized Learning:** Mobile applications can also be used for adaptive learning and to cater for learning styles and paces. These algorithms adjust educational content to the needs and abilities of each learner, offering academic resources that will enhance teaching and learning, making learning more engaging and also increasing retention. Adaptive learning can also help learner's action and provide appropriate interventions, personalized content and customized learning paths. They can also enhance motivation and confidence providing immediate feedback and support.
- 3. Collaborative Learning and Global Connections.** Mobile applications allow for global classroom collaboration, which promotes diverse perspectives, cultural exchanges and collaborative projects. Educational mobile applications offer features such as chat rooms, discussion boards, video calls, file sharing and feedback tools, which enable students to connect with peers worldwide. Collaborative learning helps students communicate, share ideas and work on project together. Example of educational mobile applications with collaborative features are EdApp, Slack and Google Drive. These apps help students learn effectively through collaboration and efficiently by leveraging the power of collaboration.
- 4. Skill Development:** It is pertinent to note that educational mobile applications help to teach students how to be skillful in terms of being tech savvy. It can also help them focus on developing soft skills like communication, teamwork, problem-solving and creativity.

Applications like EdApp, Duolingo are some that can assist one in learning languages and coding too.

2.5 Challenges of Educational Mobile Application:

One obvious challenge related to using mobile applications in education is the distraction and defocus that may occur in the aspect of teacher's use of the mobile app. It was found that the use of mobile applications can present various distractions that can reduce concentration in the teaching and learning process. Mobile apps often provide access to a variety of entertaining activities and games. However, this also has the potential to distract one from the actual teaching task.

Students may be tempted to use mobile apps for entertainment or leisure purposes rather than for actual learning. This situation can interfere with their understanding of the concepts learned and affect their academic achievement. In addition, social disruption can also occur through the use of mobile applications. Students may communicate with peers through social applications or play online games, which leads them to engage in interactions unrelated to learning. Another area for improvement in using mobile applications in education is the potential for errors or deficiencies in the learning materials provided. Although mobile applications have the potential to provide quality learning materials, there is a risk that some applications or resources may contain inaccurate or incomplete information.

Teachers who rely entirely on mobile applications for their teaching may be exposed to inaccurate information. In addition, using educational mobile applications also requires access to a mobile device and a stable internet network that if not provided, can be a barrier for teachers who need access to an adequate internet device or network at home or school. The inability to access mobile applications or the presence of interruptions in the internet network can prevent teachers from taking advantage of the teaching advantages of mobile applications.

2.6 Empirical Review

Bright, Welcome and Arthur (2024) examined the impact of using mobile technology in mathematics teaching and learning on the mathematics performance of students as mediated by students' interest in mathematics. Simple random sampling techniques were used to sample 216 students from the three selected SHS in Kumasi, Ghana. A structured questionnaire was used as an instrument for data collection since the study is purely quantitative. The results from the analysis reveal that the impact of technology on mathematics performance was positive and significant, and the impact of mathematics interest on mathematics performance was positive and significant. Also, the impact of technology on mathematics interest was positive and significant. Finally, the connection between employing technology in mathematics teaching and learning and students' performance in mathematics is somewhat mediated by students' interest in mathematics, and this relationship is statistically significant. The reviewed work takes a similar look in the aspect of examining the impact of mobile technology in learning but focused only on mathematics and the performance of student using a quantitative design while the current study evaluated the utilization of educational mobile applications in teaching among public secondary schools in Anambra state.

Wang (2024) investigated the strategies in Yuli university of Shaanxi Province for teachers' use of mobile learning applications in teaching evaluation. The interviewed students' assessment of the relationship between their teacher's use of mobile learning applications in teaching and classroom performance was identified. In this study, structured survey and quantitative analysis were used to collect and compare data. At least 375 students were randomly selected as the study sample. The results are as follows; Majority of the student respondents are male of not more than nineteen years of age representing Grade 1.2, students believe that the teachers' frequent use of the educational mobile applications in the classroom resulting to an effective utilization of the application in the teaching process. Third, female students have better assess and the utilization of mobile learning applications in their classroom than the male students.

Ching-Leng et al (2023) explored how teachers face the challenges in adopting mobile learning, in the study, experienced teacher's teaching behaviors were collected and analyzed through

sequential pattern analysis. Also, an interview with the teachers were conducted. The result showed that the teachers put a great deal of effort into creating a positive learning atmosphere. His teaching behavioral pattern in mobile learning was more scattered than that in conventional teaching mode. This might be the biggest challenge for novice teachers. Finally, this study found that the students' basic digital skills were also a vital element. The reviewed study centered on only exploring the challenges faced by teachers in adopting the mobile learning while the present study examined the utilization adoption as well the challenges and pattern of utilizing the educational mobile applications in teaching among public secondary schools in Anambra state using a mixed method research design.

Tong et al. (2023) conducted a systematic review and presented a recent synthesis of the m-learning literature from 2018 to 2023 in teacher education relating to subject publication year, geographic distribution, matter domains, mobile devices and technologies used, research methodologies used to examine the implementation of m-learning, results for pre-service teachers, as well as benefits and challenges of m-learning adoption. The study used the systematic review methodology and PRISMA guidelines. A list of 27 studies were included from several relevant studies in four, Google Scholar, Mendeley, Science Direct, and Scopus, databases using inclusion and exclusion criteria to evaluate the full text after screening the titles and abstracts. The results of this study show that m-learning has garnered interest in numerous nations worldwide, applied in different subject matter domains with the use of various mobile devices and technologies. More significantly, the findings show that using mobile learning to learn positively impacts how pre-service teachers develop their knowledge, skills, and attitudes. Additionally, adopting this learning style recently in teacher education has certain advantages and challenges, requiring lecturers, pre-service teachers, and institutions to have the necessary equipment for knowledge, skills and facilities to achieve efficiency. The reviewed work centered on systematic review following five years scope from 2018-2023 on m-learning adoption with a list of 27 studies and from several relevant studies while the present study focused on the utilization of educational mobile applications in teaching among public secondary school teachers in Anambra state.

2.7 Theoretical Framework

Diffusion of Innovation (Paul Lazarsfeld, 1955)

Diffusion of innovation is a theory that seeks to explain how, why and at what rate new ideas and technology spread through cultures. It is an extension of Two-step flow theory of Paul Lazarsfeld, Elihu Katz and their colleagues in 1955. Though its origin could be credited to contributions from different scholars across diverse fields, the theory was popularized by Everett Rogers, a professor of rural sociology in his 1962 book *Diffusion of Innovations*.

Diffusion of Innovation research centers on the conditions, which increases or decreases the likelihood that members of a given culture will adopt a new idea, product or practice. Diffusion studies are concerned with messages that convey new ideas, the process by which those ideas are conveyed and received and the extent to which those ideas are adopted and rejected. (Waston & Hill, 2006, p.80) cited in Uwakwe (2012, p.82).

Media Technology Determinism theory is a reductionist theory developed by a communication theorist and media scholar Marshall McLuhan. The theory is based on Marshal McLuhan's concept that 'The medium is the message'. McLuhan's view on medium is the message's phenomenon

simply indicates an idea that new forms of media (new media) transform our experience of ourselves and our society and this influence is ultimately more important than the content of specific messages (p.304).The theory assumes that a society's technology determines the development of its social structure and cultural values.

Media Technological determinism is the idea that technology shapes and alters basic things about behavior and society like the way we think and act, the way we conduct our interpersonal relationships, our values, the way we learn and how the society operates from one technological age to another. 'Technology' includes such things as basic tools, codes and structures for interpersonal behaviors and social institutions and modern computer and Internet technologies. In essence, it includes the whole of our material culture". (Chandler, 2000).

However, the theory was found to be relevant to the study hence the research focused on the awareness, knowledge and utilization of educational mobile applications in teaching among public secondary school teachers in Anambra state.

3.1 Research Methodology

The study employed a quantitative research design (Survey).It is also an investigation in which a part of population is studied and the selection is made such that the sample represents the entire population.

3.2 Area of Study

The area of study was Anambra state, south-east, Nigeria. The state is bounded by Abia, Imo, Enugu, Delta and Kogi states. It is one of the Igbo-speaking states in Nigeria. Anambra state has three senatorial zones and a total of twenty-one local government areas. Anambra state has a total of 230 public secondary schools. In these public schools, there are students and teachers from different backgrounds, ethnic and religious background which may tend to influence their level of awareness to the use of educational mobile applications.

3.3 Population of the Study

The population of this study consists of all public secondary school teachers in Anambra state, Nigeria. Therefore, the overall population was 5,523 persons comprising of the total number of teachers in public secondary schools in Anambra state. (PPSSC, 2024)

The population according to official data sourced from the Post –Primary Secondary school commission, is broken down thus;

Table 1: Teachers' Population

S/N	State	Category	Population	Date Retrieved
1.	Anambra	Teachers Population	5, 523	14 th May,2024
2.	Anambra	Schools Population	230	14 th May,2024

Source: Post Primary Secondary School Commission (PPSSC, Awka) 14th May, 2024

The justification for this selection was hinged on the notion that these public secondary schools are government owned and is believed to represent the decisions of the government and may also have more experienced teachers both by years of teaching and service that was needed to generate data.

3.4 Sampling Frame

The Sampling frame comprises of all the public secondary schools in Anambra State. Consequently, it was grouped according to the six educational zones in the state thus; the table underneath, presents them.

Table 2: Sampling Frame

S/N	ZONES	L.G.A	NO OF PUBLIC SCHOOLS
1.	AGUATA	Aguata	23
		Orumba North	14
		Orumba South	13
2.	AWKA	Anaocha	12
		Awka North	8
		Awka South	19
		Dunukofia	7
		Njikoka	8
3.	NNEWI	Ekwusigo	6
		Ihiala	14
		Nnewi North	7
		Nnewi South	17
4.	OGIDI	Idemili North	13
		Idemili South	8
		Oyi	9
5.	ONITSHA	Ogbaru	10
		Onitsha North	13
		Onitsha South	5
6.	OTUOCHA	Anambra East	8
		Anambra West	7
		Ayamelum	9
	TOTAL		230

Source: Post Primary Secondary School Commission (PPSSC, Awka) 14th May, 2024

Selection of the Zones

The researcher selected one from each of the zones; thus

S/N	State	Zone
1.	Anambra	Awka
2.	Anambra	Onitsha
3.	Anambra	Ogidi

The aforementioned educational zones were selected through a simple random sampling whereby the six (6) educational zones were given equal chance of being selected. The teachers who teach in these public secondary schools were selected, thus;

In the first multi-stage for teachers population, three (3) educational zones were selected through a simple random sampling; the second stage was the selection of only the Local Government Areas that represented the zones, the following stage was the selection of public secondary schools

through a simple random sampling of all the public secondary schools existing in the educational zones, the subsequent stage was the selection of class teachers from each of the selected public secondary schools using a simple random sampling.

This decision was illustrated underneath;

3.5 Sample Size and Sampling Procedure

Since the total population is up to one thousand and not up to ten thousand, the sample size for this study is 399, with 5% error margin and 99% confidence level, this was derived from the sample sizes table worked out by Krejcie and Morgan (1970)

Based on the sample formulae worked out by Research Advisors (2006), a sample size of 399 was justified for this study with population size of five thousand, five hundred and twenty three (5,523). For the survey design, the sampling procedure was the proportional sampling procedure. The study adopted the proportional sampling procedure which helped to share the sample size among the selected public secondary school teachers in appropriate proportion. This statistics helped to provide the appropriate sample size for the selected public secondary school teachers.

$$X = \frac{n}{N} \times \frac{\text{Suggested sample size (399)}}{1}$$

Where X = the proportion of sample to be allotted for each school.

n= the population of the Teachers

N=the overall population of all the Teachers

In view of the above formula, the sample size for each school

$$X = \frac{64}{5523} \times \frac{\text{Suggested Sample Size (399)}}{1} = 132$$

$$X = \frac{57}{5523} \times \frac{\text{Suggested Sample Size (399)}}{1} = 118$$

$$X = \frac{72}{5523} \times \frac{\text{Suggested Sample Size (399)}}{1} = 149$$

The copies of the questionnaire were distributed to the teachers. Data administration and collection took place after the approval of the questionnaire by the supervisor and lasted for two months. Two research assistants were engaged for this purpose. They helped in distributing and collecting copies of the questionnaire that were distributed.

3.6 Method of Data Analysis

Quantitative data emanating from 'survey' was analyzed using some descriptive statistics encompassing the frequency distribution and percentages.

3.7 Data Presentation and Analysis

Data survey were presented, analyzed and interpreted while those of survey were analyzed using descriptive statistics presented and analyzed. All this exercise yielded answers to the research questions.

Figure 1: Respondents' Sex

Figure 2 above showed that out of the (n=332) respondents (n=222) which represents 67% were females while (n=110) which represents 33% were males. This shows that the study had more females than males as respondents. However, the ratio of female to male respondents is relatively proportionate. Furthermore, this findings correlates with the findings of the study by Arikewuyo (2013) which stated that 63.2% of primary school teachers in Nigeria are females and recommended a need to attract more male teachers to the profession.

However, the findings of the study align with the existing literature which indicates that there is still unbalanced gender distribution in the public secondary schools in Anambra state and this may be attributed in the disparity to societal, economic and cultural factors, recommending a balanced

distribution of gender during recruitment and adequate remuneration to encourage more males into the teaching profession. From the data generated also, showed that despite the fewer number of male teachers in public secondary school, they have better knowledge on how to utilize some of these mobile application. This findings also supports the findings of the study by Can et al., (2019) which stated that males have an ease of use towards mobile learning especially in this new media era.

Figure 2: Respondents' Age Distribution

Figure 2 above showed that out of the (n=332) respondents, respondents at age 20-30 were predominant at 12% (n=40). Then (n=158) which accounts for 47% were between the ages of 31-40, and (n=134) which accounts for 40 % were between the ages of 41-60.

It can be deduced from the data presented above that respondents of ages 31-40, make up a greater percentage followed by the respondents of ages 41-60 of the public secondary schools in Anambra state.

However, respondents from ages 20-30 were of relatively insignificant number. This findings stipulates that the middle age staff are high and expectedly, should adopt the use of educational mobile applications in teaching and gradually made known to all group of staff especially the respondents between the ages of 41-60. This finding aligns with the study by Tong et al (2023) which should that pre-science teachers who were younger were more skilled and developed more knowledge with the adoption and utilization of mobile application in teaching.

Figure3: Respondents' Class of Teaching

Figure 3 above showed that out of the (n=332) respondents, respondents who teach JSS1-2 were predominant at 26%, then respondents who teach JSS3-SS1 (n=90) accounts for 27 % and the last set of respondents were those who teach SS2 and SS3 (n=156) which represents 47%. It can be deduced from the data presented above that respondents who teach SS2 and SS3 make up greater percentage followed by the respondents who teach JSS3 and SS1 and the respondents who teach JSS1 and JSS2 were 26% percent's of the respondents.

However, the findings stipulates that, the respondents who teach SS2 and SS3 were more and from the data generated from the in-depth interview guide, some schools have more than one teacher for some subjects offered in SS2 and SS3 especially for the SS3 students as believed to be preparing for the external examination and need more attention to make excellent grades. (See Appendix III A)

Figure 4: Respondents Years of Experience

Figure 4 above shows that from the (n=332) respondents, (n=133) which represents 47% are between the years of 1-10, while (n=86) are between the years of 11-20 which represents 26%, then the third group of years (n=73) which accounts for 22% are respondents that have up to 21-30 years of experience and the respondents (n=37) which accounts for 12% are respondents who have 31 to 35 years of experience.

This data goes to mean that teachers between one to ten years of experience are more and expected to be people who are younger in the field and should be abreast with the adoption of new media in teaching profession. However, the ratio of these years of experience is relatively proportionate.

Figure 5: Respondents' location of school.

Figure 5 above shows that from the respondents (n=332), respondents (n=212) which accounts for 64 % are respondents whose schools are located in an urban area, while respondents (n=120) which accounts for 36% are respondents whose schools are located in a rural area. This data posits that many respondents have their schools located in urban areas and is expected to be abreast with the use of new media.

Supporting this view, is the theory of diffusion of innovations by Everett Rogers which suggests that the adoption of new technologies or innovations follows a predictable pattern. According to this theory, urban areas tend to have more; early adopters, access to information, social network and infrastructure. This means that location of the school plays a key role in adopting the utilization of educational mobile applications in teaching.

Figure 6: Respondents' Subject Department

Figure 6 above shows that from the respondents (n=332), respondents (n=212) which accounts for 64% are respondents who belong to the science and science related departments, while respondents (n=120) which accounts for 36% are respondents who belong to the Arts or Arts related department. This data posits that many respondents who are of the science or science related departments are from schools located in urban areas and is expected to be abreast with the adoption of new media in teaching.

Supporting this view, is the theory of diffusion of innovations by Everest Rogers which suggests that the adoption of new technologies or innovations follows a predictable pattern. According to this theory, urban areas tend to have more; early adopters, access to information, social network and infrastructure.

Table 4: Respondents' Knowledge and awareness of educational mobile app in teaching.
Do you have a functional ICT laboratory in your school?

Responses	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Yes, we have	N=172	52
No, we don't	N= 120	36
Can't say	N=40	12

Total	N= 332	100
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Source: Field survey, (2025)

Table 4 above reveals that (n=172) respondents representing 52% have functional ICT laboratory in their school while (n=120) respondents representing 36% do not have a functional ICT laboratory in their school while (n=40) representing 12% indicated that they do not have a functional ICT laboratory in their schools. This implies that many respondents have a functional ICT laboratory and expected to be utilizing it in their teaching. This indicates that there is a considerable level of awareness of ICT utilization among respondents even though some of them (12%) are still not aware of such educational mobile applications that can be utilized in teaching.

Table 5: Respondents' exposure to educational mobile applications in teaching.

Responses	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Yes ,I have seen	N=126	38
No, I haven't seen	N=205	62
Total	N=332	100

Source: Field survey, 2025

Table 5 shows that (n=126) respondents representing 38% actually confirmed that they are exposed to the benefits of utilizing educational mobile applications in teaching, while (n=205) respondents representing 62% indicated that they have not seen an educational mobile applications utilized for teaching, this shows that these respondents lack exposure to educational mobile applications. In comparison of the data from table 5 and table 4, one can say that although some of the respondents have seen educational mobile applications but may not be exposed to the benefits of utilizing educational mobile applications in teaching. This means that the benefits of utilizing educational mobile applications are not well known by the public secondary school teachers and can connote a factor for low utilization of educational applications.

This finding also supports the theory of diffusion of innovation utilized in this study, which states that new ideas can spread within the society as long as certain conditions are put in place .one of the conditions is that the relative advantage (benefits) from propagation(utilization) is known and this can be done through organizing seminars and workshops for the teachers as seen from some of the responses of the interviewees that this exposure can come through seminars and workshops, which is yet to be organized to this regard.

Table 6: Respondents' utilization of educational mobile applications in teaching

Responses	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Yes, we do	N=136	34
No, we don't	N=196	66
Total	N=332	100

Source: Field survey, 2025

Table 6 above (n=136) of the respondents which represents 34% indicated that they utilize educational mobile applications in teaching while (n=196) respondents which represents 66% indicated that they do not utilize educational mobile applications in teaching in their schools. From the data sourced, one can say that a greater percentage of the public secondary school teachers do not utilize educational mobile applications in teaching, this goes to mean that majority are yet to adopt the utilization of educational mobile applications in teaching which could be as a result of poor awareness and knowledge of educational mobile applications.

However, if there is knowledge of utilization, there should be an expected level of utilization of educational mobile applications in teaching which is believed to make teaching more effective and easier.

Table 7: Respondents' thoughts on benefits for utilization of educational mobile applications in teaching

Responses	Frequency	Percentage (%)
For Effective Teaching	N=139	42
For covering of scheme	N=40	12
To enhance learning	N=153	46
Total	N= 332	100

Source: Field survey, 2025

From the data in table 7 above, (n=139) which represent 42% indicated that their perceived gains of utilizing educational mobile applications is for effective teaching, while (n=40) which represent 12% indicated that covering of scheme is their perceived gain of adopting the utilization of educational mobile applications, while respondents (n=153) representing 46% indicated that enhancing learning is the benefits for adopting the utilization of educational mobile applications in teaching.

Table 8: Respondents' challenge in utilization of educational mobile application in teaching

Responses	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Yes, I do	N=186	56
No, I don't	N=146	44
Total	N=332	100

Source: Field survey, 2025

From the data generated from table 8, it showed the responses on challenges by the respondents, (n=186) which represent 56% indicated that they have a challenge adopting the educational mobile applications while (n=146) representing 44% indicated that they do not encounter challenges in adopting educational mobile applications in teaching. Looking at the percentage of the challenges, one can say that a good number of these public secondary school teachers have one challenge or the other as regards adopting the educational mobile applications in teaching, which could be a key factor for low utilization of educational mobile applications in teaching. These also aligns with one of the theory utilized in this study which is the diffusion of innovation theory, indicating that there are stages of adoption of a new media and not everyone could be in the category of early adopters and that one's environment could also contribute to the ability of the new media to spread through a given region.

Table 9: Respondents' specific challenge in utilization of educational mobile applications in teaching

Responses	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Low knowledge of educational mobile apps	N=66	20
Poor internet access	N=73	22
Low availability of mobile device	N=40	12

Poor training/seminar	N=110	33
Others	N=43	13
Total	N=332	100

From the table 9 above (n=66) representing 20% indicated their challenge was low knowledge of educational mobile applications, while (n=73) respondents representing 22% indicated that poor internet access is a challenge to adoption of utilization of educational mobile applications, (n=40) which represent 12% indicated that low availability of mobile devices needed is a challenge to utilization of educational mobile applications (n=110) which represent 33% indicated that, they are yet to receive any training or seminar to this regard, (n=43) which represent 13% indicated others which can be deduced to state that there may be other challenges that are encountered by the public secondary school teachers in a bid to adopt this educational mobile applications in teaching.

Discussion of Findings

Findings of the study revealed that the public secondary school teachers in Anambra state are averagely knowledgeable of the educational mobile applications utilization in teaching. This is made evident in the responses of the respondents from the survey and also from the interview sessions where respondents of a percentage of 52 (n=172) stated that they have knowledge of educational mobile applications and in all the interview sessions where the interviewees stated that they know about the new apps that are teacher friendly although about four of the respondents stated that it is not a deep knowledge but with the fact that there are technological advances and we are in the digital era. Furthermore, data extracted from tables 15-20 show that, there is an average level of knowledge of educational mobile applications utilization among public secondary school teachers in Anambra state.

The current study makes a conceptual contribution on the relevance of educational mobile applications in teaching. From the data generated from the questionnaire, about 36% (n=120) stated that they are not aware of the educational mobile application utilization in teaching.

Furthermore, this low awareness of educational mobile applications can be said to be a factor for low utilization. This finding goes in line with the theory of diffusion of innovation utilized in the study to say that for effective utilization of a new media or new ideas to spread within the society, certain conditions must be in place. These conditions include; that the idea must be seen (exposure) known (knowledge) relatively advantageous (benefits) and that proper channel exists for its propagation (utilization). This perception would be a function of the extent to which they have become familiar with the innovation (i.e) how much the innovation has diffused amongst them. In other words, their utilization of educational mobile applications would be influenced by the extent they have become familiar with it, its knowledge, implications and benefits in teaching. This means that for effective adoption and utilization, it is needful to have a high level of knowledge of educational mobile applications in teaching and be aware of the benefits in teaching.

From the findings of the study and the literature that they are specific areas that these public secondary school utilizes the educational mobile applications amongst the few percentage of the respondents that indicated a knowledge of it are as a result of having a motivation for using it. For example, the few public secondary school teachers from the science department indicated that they utilize it to show the students some practical videos that will enhance the student's understanding of the topics under study. The main motivation for using the educational mobile applications in teaching is due to the learning interest of the student as it also assist teachers to teach with ease, hence is been referred to as teacher-friendly app. It can also be used to show images of things that may be not be good if written or talked about only. That is to say that they may have a knowledge of other new media devices which they adopt for different purposes.

There is however some constraints that the respondents stated as the challenges that they encounter in utilizing the educational mobile applications in teaching. The findings of the study showed that these challenges include poor availability of needed mobile device, poor availability of internet access, little or no knowledge of mobile app usage, lack of trainings through workshops.

5.1 CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of this study, the researcher concludes thus;

Educational mobile applications with its perceived benefits especially as it helps to make teaching easier and impactful should be adopted over others. Creativity and ideas are new values that attracts people to accept a particular message irrespective of the means of communication. However, these public secondary school teachers should adopt these educational mobile applications as an alternative means to teach the students and be adopted as a formal way of carrying out the duty of teaching and also teaching student to engage their time using these educational mobile applications.

In addition, it seems to appear that the public secondary school teachers ability to effectively adopt and utilize these educational mobile applications in teaching to a large extent is dependent on been fully aware, oriented and exposed to the benefits of utilizing educational mobile applications which could be through constant workshop and training and providing facilities to enable its adoption and utilization. This will go a long way to improve and encourage proper utilization which aids poor understanding of lesson taught and increase learning prowess among students.

In view of the research significance, this work contributes to the existing knowledge of educational mobile applications utilization among public secondary school teachers on the relevance of utilizing educational mobile applications in teaching hence as seen in this study and in the reviewed literature and if effectively utilized could go a long way to possibly reduce the cognitive stress and environmental effects posed on teachers through the academic workload they carry. It will enlighten the public secondary teachers on how to improve their teaching profession through adopting the use of educational mobile applications which will help to manage teaching in the absence of the teacher.

5.3 Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, a number of recommendations were found relevant towards the effective utilization of educational mobile applications in teaching.

Public secondary school teachers should also increase their utilization of educational mobile applications particularly for teaching purposes. This will help make educational mobile applications utilization in teaching a professional one, so that teachers can only feel satisfied to utilize it whenever there is need for it especially to breach geographical divide and foster understanding of the lesson taught as observed that a greater number do not utilize it for educational purposes.

There is a necessity to increase the awareness on the importance and benefits of utilizing educational mobile applications in teaching among public secondary school teachers. Proper orientation should be encouraged towards achieving effective utilization of educational mobile applications in teaching profession.

Public secondary school teachers should be sensitized by the government through the ministry of education in the state on the emerging trend of educational mobile applications utilization in teaching to avoid inducing negatively from them.

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